

BIR ÓLCHOVLI ISSIQLIK ÓTKAZUVCHANLIK TENGLAMASI UCHUN UCHINCHI TUR ARALASH MASALANI FURYE USULI BILAN YECHILISHI

Xaqbergenova Nargiza Fazil qızı

Qoraqalpoq davlat universiteti, 3-bosqich bakalavr talabasi

Ushbu

$$u_t = a^2 u_{xx} + bu_x + cu + f(x, t) \quad (1)$$

tenglama uchun $0 < x < l$, $t > 0$ yarim yo'lakda quyidagi

$$u|_{x=0} = 0, u_x|_{x=l} = 0 \quad (2)$$

chegaraviy shartlari va

$$u|_{t=0} = \varphi(x) \quad (3)$$

boshlang'ich sharti bilan yechimi topilsin.

Yechimni Furye usuli bo'yicha ikkita funksiyaning ko'paytmasi, ya'ni

$$u(x, t) = X(x) \cdot T(t) \quad (4)$$

kórinishida izlaymiz va uni (1) tenglama qo'ysak

$$T'(t) \cdot X(x) = a^2 T(t) \cdot X''(x) + bT(t) \cdot X'(x) + cT(t) \cdot X(x) + f(x, t)$$

tengligi hosil bo'ladi va uni $a^2 T(t) \cdot X(x)$ ifodasiga bo'lib soddalashtiramiz va

uni $-\lambda^2$ parametrga teng deb qaraymiz.

$$\frac{T'(t)}{a^2 T(t)} - c - \frac{f(x, t)}{a^2 T(t) X(x)} = \frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} + \frac{bX'(x)}{a^2 X(x)} = -\lambda^2 \quad (5)$$

Endi, (2) chegaraviy shartlardan va (5) foydalanib $X(x)$ xos funksiyaning ko'rinishini topiladi, ya'ni quyidagi chegaraviy masalaning notrival yechimini topamiz

$$X''(x) + \frac{b}{a^2} X'(x) + \lambda^2 X(x) = 0, X(0) = X'(l) = 0 \quad (6)$$

Bu chegaraviy masalaning yechimi

$$X_k(x) = e^{-\frac{b}{2a^2}x} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi k}{l} x \quad (7)$$

Bu yerda, xos funksiyaning xos sonlari - $\lambda_k^2 = \frac{b^2}{4a^2} + \frac{\pi^2 k^2 a^2}{l^2}$ $k \in \mathbb{N}$

Endi $f(x, t)$ funksiyaning x va t ning funksiyalari ko'paytmasi deb qarab, Fuyre qatoriga yoyamiz, yani

$$f(x, t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f_k(t) \cdot e^{-\frac{b}{2a^2}x} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi k}{l} x \quad (8)$$

bu yerda

$$f_k(t) = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l f(x, t) e^{-\frac{b}{2a^2}x} \cos \left(\frac{\pi k}{l} x \right) dx.$$

(4) yechimning umumiy qator ko'rinishini (5) tenglamaga qo'yib, (8) ni e'tiborga olsak,

$$\frac{T'_k(t)}{a^2 T_k(t)} - c - \frac{f_k(t)}{a^2 T_k(t)} = -\lambda_k^2$$

ya'ni quyidagi birinchi tartibli chiziqli tenglamani olamiz

$$T'_k(t) + a^2 (\lambda_k^2 - c) T_k(t) = f_k(t) \quad (9)$$

va bu tenglamaning yechimi

$$T_k(t) = e^{-(\lambda_k^2 - a^2 c)t} \left[C_k + \int e^{-(\lambda_k^2 - a^2 c)t} f_k(t) dt \right] \quad (10)$$

Berilgen (1) tenglamaning (3) boshlang'ich shartidan foylanib,

$$u(x, 0) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} T_k(0) e^{-\frac{b}{2a^2}x} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi k}{l} x = \varphi(x)$$

ya'ni

$$T_k(0) = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l \varphi(x) e^{-\frac{b}{2a^2}x} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi k}{l} x dx \quad (11)$$

(10) oddiy differensial tenglamaning (11) boshlang'ich sharti hosil b'oladi.

(11) tenglikdan foydalanib, (10) tenglikdagi noma'lum bo'lgan C_k sonlarining qiymati topiladi, ya'ni

$$C_k = T_k(0)e^{-(\lambda_k^2 - a^2c)t} - \left(\int e^{-(\lambda_k^2 - a^2c)t} f_k(t) dt \right) \Big|_{t=0} \quad (12)$$

bo'ladi. Demak (1)-(3) aralash masalaning

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} e^{-(\lambda_k^2 - a^2c)t} \left[C_k + \int e^{(\lambda_k^2 - a^2c)t} f_k(t) dt \right] e^{-\frac{b}{2a^2}x} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi k}{l} x \quad (13)$$

ko'rinishdagi yechimi topiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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